

Synthesis of Thiosemicarbazones of Some Aromatic Fluoro-Ketones as Potential Pesticides

K. C. Joshi and S. C. Bahel

Semicarbazones of several ketones and aldehydes have been reported to be toxic as stomach poisons to codling moth larvae¹. Thiosemicarbazones of many ketones and chalcones have been found to possess antifungal and antibacterial properties². Several aromatic fluoro-ketones, synthesised earlier³, as possible pesticides, have therefore been converted into their thiosemicarbazones in order to combine the toxicity of the ketone molecule with that of thiosemicarbazide possessing the toxophoric 'N—C—S' grouping. The thiosemicarbazones prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl.No.	Ketone used.	Thiosemicarbazone.		% Sulphur.	
		Formula.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Fluoro-A	$C_9H_{10}N_3FS$	168°	14.76	15.16
2	5-Methyl-4-fluoro-A	$C_{10}H_{12}N_3FS$	178°	13.85	14.22
3	5-Methyl-2-fluoro-A	$C_{10}H_{12}N_3FS$	110°	13.92	14.22
4	4-Fluoro-P	$C_{10}H_{12}N_3FS$	168°	13.69	14.22
5	2-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl propenyl K	$C_{11}H_{12}ON_3FS$	*	12.26	12.64
6	5-Methyl-2-fluoro-P	$C_{11}H_{14}N_3FS$	*	12.56	13.38
7	4-Fluoro-B	$C_{11}H_{14}N_3FS$	112°	13.02	13.39
8	5-Methyl-2-fluoro-B	$C_{12}H_{16}N_3FS$	*	12.08	12.64
9	2-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl 2'-chlorophenyl K	$C_{14}H_{11}ON_3ClFS$	*80°	9.16	9.89
10	2-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl 4'-fluorophenyl K	$C_{14}H_{11}ON_3F_2S$	*78°	9.86	10.42
11	2-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl anisyl K	$C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_3FS$	158°	10.52	10.03
12	2-Hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl heptyl K	$C_{15}H_{20}ON_3FS$	*90°	9.82	10.28
13	2-Fluoro-5-methyl- α -phenyl-A	$C_{16}H_{16}N_3FS$	*	10.15	10.63

Where temperatures have been recorded, the compounds decompose; in other cases they are viscous and decompose during distillation; sulphur in these compounds has been estimated before distillation. A=acetophenone; B=butyrophenone; K=ketone; P=propiofenone.

1. Siegler *et al.*, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1942, **35**, 74.
2. Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 713.
3. Joshi and Bahel, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 121; 1960, **37**, 487.

General Method of Preparation.—The thiosemicarbazones were prepared by following the method of Campaigne *et al.*⁴. The appropriate ketone (0.1*M*) was dissolved in 50% ethanol (100 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2ml) and thiosemicarbazide (0.1*M*) were added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 2 hrs. and then cooled. The product, wherever possible, was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The pesticidal properties of the compounds will be communicated in due course.

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ORGANIC CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
GORAKHPUR UNIVERSITY,
GORAKHPUR, U. P.

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4. Campaigne *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 688.